

Prevalence of *S.aureus* and *P.aeruginosa* strains isolated from pneumonic calves

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ABSTRACT

Bovine respiratory disease (BRD) is a great financial issue in cattle husbandry, particularly in young and feedlot animals throughout the world. This study was planned to investigate the prevalence and antibiotic resistance of *S.aureus* and *P. aeruginosa* strains causing respiratory disorders in calves, a total of 100 samples were collected from pneumonic calves at private farms in sharkia province, Arab Republic of Egypt. Various specimens were subjected to microbiological examination where prevalence of *S.aureus* was 13% and the prevalence of *P.aeruginosa* was 6% . The isolated strains were subjected to the antibiotic sensitivity test. The results revealed that the isolated *S.aureus* strains were sensitive to gentamicin, enrofloxacin (95%) and erythromycin (85%). The isolated *P.aeruginosa* strains were highly sensitive to enrofloxacin, norfloxacin (95%) and gentamicin (90%) and highly resistant to erythromycin (100%) and ampicillin (90%). Briefly, *S.aureus* and *P.aeruginosa* are predominant bacterial pathogens incriminated in respiratory disease in calves. In addition, the continuous application of antibacterial susceptibility testing is essential for selection of the most effective antibiotics.

Key words: pneumonia, *S.aureus*, *P. aeruginosa*, calves, antibiotic resistance.

Introduction

Respiratory diseases are the most frequently recorded causes of morbidity and mortality in calves. Respiratory affections are a complex syndrome involving stress factors, environmental factors, bacterial, fungal and viral infections. They generally develop when a calf's immune system is compromised or if the calf has a concurrent viral or mycoplasmal infection (Shahrour, 2003). In addition, diverse environmental conditions can predispose to the disease (Hafez et al., 1991). Also, management practices may cause respiratory tract problems associated with high mortality rates (Highlander, 2001). Different pneumonic pathogens but less frequently could be recovered from pneumonic lungs are *S.aureus*, *P.aeruginosa* (Clavijo et al., 2007 and Baker, 2008). Bovine respiratory disease (BRD) causes severe clinical symptoms in animals. The most frequent symptoms observed in diseased calves are hurried respiration, abdominal breathing,

serous to purulent nasal and ocular discharge, coughing, fever, anorexia, dehydration and retarded growth (Snowder et al., 2006; Leruste et al., 2012; Pardon et al., 2012; Visser, 2016). Enzootic pneumonia is a great problem in calves less than 6 months old with peak incidence from 2 to 10 weeks, however, may be detected in calves till 1 year of age. It is more common problem in veal calves, dairy, and housed calves. Peak incidence of disease can decrease passively acquired immunity. Mortality rates may reach 100% while the case fatality rates are variable but can reach 20% (Merck and merial, 2002). The present work was aimed to detect the prevalence of *S.aureus* and *P.aeruginosa* in pneumonic calves as well as detection of antibiotic susceptibility of these isolated strains

Material and methods:

Sampling

In this study, a total number of 100 nasal swabs were collected from pneumonic calves of different ages at private farms in

Sharkia province, Arab Republic of Egypt. All specimens were collected in sterile polyethylene bags as well as peptone broth as transport media for further microbiological examination.

Bacteriological examination:

The collected specimens (nasal swabs) were inoculated into peptone broth then tubes were incubated at 37°C for 24 h. Loopful from broth culture was streaked onto Nutrient agar, and Mannitol salt agar and Blood agar, then plates were incubated at 37°C for 48h. at aerobic condition. Typical bacterial colonies were identified depending upon microscopical examination by using Gram’s stain, culture characters and biochemical reactions according to (Cowan and Steel, 1993).

Antibiotic sensitivity testing

The susceptibility to various antimicrobial agents (erythromycin, gentamicin, norfloxacin, tetracycline, amoxicillin, streptomycin, trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole, ampicillin enrofloxacin) was carried out according to **Finegold and Martin (1982)** using Disc diffusion method.

Results:

Clinical examination of calves showing respiratory manifestations

Diseased calves showed a rectal temperature of at least 40°C, anorexia, and clinical respiratory signs such as dyspnea, nasal discharge, cough and depression.

Prevalence of *S.aureus* and *P.aeruginosa* in pneumonic calves

As described in Table (1), the microbiological examination of 100 nasal swabs were collected from pneumonic calves revealed that the prevalence of *S.aureus* 13% (n=13) and *P. aeruginosa* 6% (n=6).

Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of the isolated strains:

Regarding the antibiotic sensitivity testing, as described in Tables (2 and 3) the results revealed that the isolated *S.aureus* strains were sensitive to gentamicin, enrofloxacin (95% each) and erythromycin (85%). The isolated *P.aeruginosa* strains were highly sensitive to enrofloxacin, norfloxacin (95%) and gentamicin (90%) and highly resistant to erythromycin (100%) and ampicillin (90%).

Table (1): Prevalence of *S.aureus* and *P.aeruginosa* strains isolated from pneumonic calves:

Isolated spp.	No. of strains	%
<i>S.aureus</i>	13	13
<i>P.aeruginosa</i>	6	6

(2): Antimicrobial sensitivity of *S.aureus* isolated from calves.

Antimicrobial Agents	Disc Concentration	Resistant		Intermediate		Sensitive	
		No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
Ampicillin	10µg	5	50	3	30	2	20
Amoxicillin	20µg	9	90	1	10	0	0
Erythromycin	15µg	2	5	0	0	8	85
Enrofloxacin	5µg	0	0	1	5	9	95
Gentamicin	10µg	0	0	1	5	9	95
Norofloxacin	10µg	1	10	5	50	4	40
Streptomycin	10µg	5	50	4	40	1	10
Tetracycline	30µg	7	70	1	10	2	20
Trimethoprim-Sulphametho-xazol	1.25+23.75µg	3	30	2	20	5	50

Table (3) Antimicrobial sensitivity of *P.aeruginosa* isolated from calves

Antimicrobial Agents	Disc Concentration	Resistant		Intermediate		Sensitive	
		No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
Ampicillin	10µg	4	90	1	10	0	0
Amoxicillin	20µg	1	25	3	50	1	25
Erythromycin	15µg	5	100	0	0	0	0
Enrofloxacin	5µg	0	0	1	5	4	95
Gentamicin	10µg	0	0	1	10	4	90
Norofloxacin	10µg	0	0	1	5	4	95
Streptomycin	10µg	0	0	1	30	4	70
Tetracycline	30µg	4	85	1	15	0	0
Trimethoprim-Sulphametho-xazol	1.25+23.75µg	1	20	2	40	2	40

DISCUSSION:

Bovine respiratory disease (BRD) is a great financial issue in cattle husbandry, particularly in young and feedlot animals throughout the world (Adamu, 2007). In the present work, the prevalence of *S.aureus* was (13%) in pneumonic calves. These results agree with those obtained by (Shahrour, 2003; Wessely et al., 2005; Clavijo et al., 2007 and Sayed and Zaitoun 2009; Enany et al., 2012). *S.aureus* resides in the upper respiratory tract and is involved in disease processes only when stress conditions prevail (Baker, 2008). Depending upon the activity of coagulase enzyme produced by *S.aureus* resulted in clot formation in rabbit plasma (Kloos and Schleifer, 1986). Contrariwise, staphylokinase produced by certain strains of *S.aureus* has been shown to have profibrinolytic properties and act as plasminogen activator enhancing the activity of endogenous fibrinolytic system (Collen and Linjen, 1991). In the current study, the prevalence of *P.aeruginosa* was (6%) in pneumonic calves. These results are similar to those obtained by (Pineda et al., 2003; KILIÇ and MUZ 2004). Although *P.aeruginosa* is usually accepted as an opportunistic pathogen, it can cause pneumonia in cattle (Quinn et al., 2002). Regarding the antibiogram, the isolated *S. aureus* strains were highly sensitive to gentamicin, enrofloxacin (95% each) and erythromycin (85%). In this concern, Selim

et al. (1998) recorded that *Staphylococcus* species isolated from milk samples were sensitive to gentamicin and cephaloridine. Beiter et al. (2006) recorded that *S. aureus* was highly sensitive to enrofloxacin. On the other hand, 70% of *S.aureus* strains were resistant to tetracycline (Schwarz et al., 1998). In addition, the isolated *P.aeruginosa* strains were susceptible to enrofloxacin, norfloxacin with a percentage (95% each) and gentamicin (90%) and were resistant to erythromycin, ampicillin and tetracycline. Shahrour (2003) reported about the high prevalence of resistance among *P.aeruginosa* to antibiotics and sulphonamides. The multi-resistance property of *P.aeruginosa* was reported also by Radostits et al. (2007) and may be attributed to physicochemical properties of the cell wall rather than antibiotic inhibitory enzymes. This coincides with Myers et al. (1985) and El-haenawy et al. (1994) who stated that *P.aeruginosa* was resistant to all antibiotics tested. 100% of the strains were completely sensitive to gentamicin, norfloxacin and tobramycin. Briefly, *S.aureus* and *P.aeruginosa* are predominant bacterial pathogens incriminated in respiratory disease in calves. In addition, the continuous application of antibacterial susceptibility testing is essential for selection of the most effective antibiotics.

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